

Complex Formation in the Ternary Systems of Beryllium(II)-Methylmalonic, Dimethylmalonic and Some Dicarboxylic Acids*

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Manuscript received 24 March 1982, accepted 10 December 1982

The stability constants of binary and mixed methyl substituted malonic-dicarboxylic acid complexes of beryllium(II) have been determined. The substituted malonic acids are methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic and the dicarboxylic acids are succinic, itaconic, maleic, glutaric and adipic. Beryllium(II) forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with all the ligands except glutaric and adipic in pH range 2.75-5.50.

Ternary chelates of beryllium(II)-methylmalonic-dicarboxylic and beryllium(II)-dimethylmalonic-dicarboxylic acid systems have been studied. Ternary complex formation is discussed on the basis of ring size, nature of the substituents in the ligands, equilibrium constants and coordination chemistry of beryllium(II). It is observed that the complex stability and ligand basicity gives straight line relationship.

THE simple binary complexes of beryllium(II) with a variety of ligands^{1,2} particularly dicarboxylic acids and their resulting structures, and in recent years, the coordination behaviour of beryllium ion have been reported by Thomas-David *et al*³⁻⁷. Binary and ternary complexes of beryllium(II)-iminodiacetic acid with some simple dicarboxylic and hydroxy acids have been studied by Chaturvedi *et al*⁸. The mixed-ligand complexes of Be(II)-salicylic with substituted salicylic acids complexes are also reported⁹.

We have recently reported the results of extensive investigation of metal complexes and mixed complexes of sulphur containing ligands¹⁰⁻¹⁴, which allow a systematic characterization of their binding modes¹¹, as well as the effect of substituent groups on methylene group of malonic acid¹⁵, in particular the early distinguished ability of dimethyl groups on the ground of steric factors and the possibility of distinguishing O-O from N-O and S-O coordination on the basis of stability constant data. In the present work, we sought to determine the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes of beryllium(II) with methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic and some dicarboxylic acids and to examine the complexing tendency of dicarboxylic acids with 1:1 Be²⁺-methylmalonic and Be²⁺-dimethylmalonic acid complexes.

Experimental

Materials: The dicarboxylic acids, methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic, succinic, itaconic, maleic, glutaric and adipic were from Fluka (Germany) or B.D.H. (AnalaR grade). Beryllium nitrate used was of B.D.H. AnalaR grade and its concentration in

solution was estimated gravimetrically¹⁶. All solutions were prepared in glass distilled water. The other chemicals were the same as described earlier¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Measurements: Beryllium complex formation constants were evaluated from potentiometric titration curves of the methylmalonic, dimethylmalonic and other dicarboxylic acids in absence and presence of beryllium. Changes in pH were followed with an ELICO Digital pH meter, LI-10 using glass and calomel electrodes. All investigations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere at 30° and $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄). A FORTRAN computer programme was used for calculation of the formation constants and at least 150 experimental data were considered for each system. The computations were carried out with the IBM 370 computer of the Indian Institute of Technology, Madras.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants of the methylmalonic and dimethylmalonic acids and the binary stability constants of beryllium(II) complexes of these ligands, not so far studied under experimental conditions, have been determined by the method of Irving and Rossotti^{20,21}. The stability constants (log K) for beryllium complexes evaluated in the present work are presented in Table 1, along with some literature values.

Beryllium(II) forms binary *bis* complexes with all the ligands except glutaric and adipic acids in the pH range 2.5-5.0. A comparison of stability constants (Table 1) indicates that methylmalonic and maleic acid complexes are relatively more stable

* Presented at the Annual Convention of Chemists, Madras, 1981.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS (log K) FOR THE PARENT BINARY COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II)

$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$; $t = 30^\circ$

(Standard deviations are given in parentheses)

Ligand/acids	log K_1	log K_2
Methylmalonic	5.21(3)	3.46(2)
Dimethylmalonic	4.88(2)	3.40(3)
Succinic	3.18(2)	1.65(4)
	3.08 ^a	—
	2.72 ^b	1.62 ^b
Itaconic	3.55(2)	2.05(3)
Maleic	4.30(1)	2.11(4)
	4.33 ^c	2.13 ^c
Glutaric	3.04(1)	
Adipic	3.24(3)	
	3.24 ^c	

^aref. 15, ^bref. 33, ^cref. 32.

than the other dicarboxylic acid complexes. The nature of the coordinating atoms for the ligands is similar and the observed stability constants are in the order expected for their basicities, ring sizes and the nature of the substituents, except for dimethyl malonic acid. The destabilized nature of the dimethylmalonic acid complex is due to the steric hindrance in binary *bis*-complex of dimethylmalonic acid. The concentrations of the various species, M_2X , H_2Y , M^{2+} , MX , MX_2^- , MY , MY_2^- , MX_2Y^{2-} and different equilibrium constants were evaluated by the method of Ramamoorthy and Manning²² as outlined earlier^{14,19}. The average equilibrium constants calculated for the systems are set out in Table 2.

TABLE 2—LOGARITHMS OF EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF BERYLLIUM(II)-METHYLMALONIC/DIMETHYLMALONIC (Y)-SECONDARY (X) ACIDS

$\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$ $t = 30^\circ$

(Standard deviations are given in parentheses)

Acid/systems	β_{XY}	K_{DXY}^a	K_{2XY}	K_{2YX}	$\Delta \log K$
Methylmalonic-succinic	7.84(3)	2.18	4.66	2.63	-0.55
Methylmalonic-itaconic	8.05(2)	1.83	4.50	2.84	-0.71
Methylmalonic-maleic	8.12(4)	2.76	4.62	3.71	-0.59
Methylmalonic-glutaric	7.76(2)	1.26 ^b	4.72	2.55	-0.49
Methylmalonic-adipic	7.95(1)	1.25 ^b	4.71	2.74	-0.50
Dimethylmalonic-succinic	7.70(2)	2.29	4.52	2.82	-0.35
Dimethylmalonic-itaconic	7.33(3)	0.78	3.78	2.45	-1.10
Dimethylmalonic-maleic	8.76(2)	2.83	4.46	3.88	-0.42
Dimethylmalonic-glutaric	7.28(4)	0.84 ^b	4.24	2.40	-0.64
Dimethylmalonic-adipic	7.81(2)	1.16 ^b	4.57	2.93	-0.31

The two equilibrium constants involving mixed ligand complexes, $\Delta \log K$ (equation 1) and the disproportionation constant K_{DXY} (equation 2), is defined by Sigel²³ as

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{2XY} - \log K_{MY_2} = \log K_{2YX} - \log K_{MX_2} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{DXY} = 2 \log \beta_{MXY} - \log \beta_{MX_2} - \log \beta_{MY_2} \quad (2)$$

Thus $\Delta \log K$ is a measure of the affinity that Y has for bonding to the equated metal ion and to the complex (MX). Since more coordination sites

are available for bonding the first ligand to a metal ion than the second ligand, $\Delta \log K$ should, in general, be negative. As regards Be(II), usually having a coordination number of four, the expected value of $\Delta \log K$ would be -0.6; values markedly greater than this would suggest stabilization of ternary complex. Statistically, a value (0.6) of K_{DXY} is to be expected so that values greater than this would indicate the preferential formation of mixed-ligand complexes. The value of K_{DXY} is clearly dependent on the stabilities of the simple binary *bis*-complexes. Since these *bis*-complexes are not intermediates in the formation of ternary complexes, the value of K_{DXY} may not truly reflect the stability of ternary complex.

In all systems (Table 2), the values of $\Delta \log K$ are negative, showing the stabilized nature of ternary complexes^{24,25}. The tendency of mixed-ligand complex formation is the same in the systems methylmalonic-glutaric and methylmalonic-adipic as $\Delta \log K$ is -0.49 and -0.50, respectively. The practical use of $\Delta \log K$ is to obtain an interesting relationship between complex stability and ligand basicity for characterising the stabilities of ternary complexes. In the present work, the data fit within experimental errors on a straight line of positive slope. During the course of investigation, we reported this interesting aspect of the ternary complexes of the metal ions²⁶⁻²⁸ and in particular, copper(II)-dipeptide-amino acids²⁹. It can be seen (Fig. 1) that the point corresponding to maleic acid shows extra stabilization from expected straight lines. However, other straight lines (dotted, Fig. 1) are also possible if maleic acid is taken into consideration. Maleic acid is deviated from the expected straight lines, indicating relative stabilized nature of ternary complexes due to double bond character^{30,31}.

Fig. 1. Relation between $\Delta \log K$ and $pK_{H_2A}^H + pK_{HA}^H$ for the ternary complexes of Be(II)-methylmalonic-dicarboxylic acids (A) and Be(II)-methylmalonic-dicarboxylic acids (B); dicarboxylic acids are (1) succinic, (2) itaconic (3) maleic, (4) glutaric and (5) adipic. $\mu = 0.1 M (NaClO_4)$, $t = 30^\circ$.

From the equilibrium constant data, the values for K_{DXY} are significantly greater than 0.6 indicating that the ternary complexes are much more stable. A comparison of K_{2XY} and K_{MY_2} and K_{2YX} and

K_{MY} , values in the systems studied shows preferential formation of ternary complexes over binary.

In conclusion, we may point out that $\Delta \log K$ is appropriate for characterizing the mixed-ligand complexes. The addition of methyl groups in malonic acid to an existing substituent effect simply contributes a more sterically hindered effect experienced by the metal ions.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Prof. S. S. Pawar, Head, Chemistry Department, for his keen interest and to Dr. L. G. Pardeshi for valuable suggestions. The financial support from University Grants Commission, New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

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